

Blended Learning: A Key to Unlocking Students' Interest and Retention in Basic Science

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Abstract

The research aimed to ascertain the effect of blended learning strategy on students' interest and retention in basic science. The investigation was executed within the Aguata educational zone located in Anambra State. The sample population encompassed 2,950 upper basic VIII students in the 50 public secondary institutions within the specified zone. The study's sample size was 97 students (39 males & 58 females). The researchers used sample random sampling to select two local government areas for the educational zone used for this study, along with purposive sampling to select two co-educational schools with one intact class randomly assigned to the experimental and control groups. Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT) and the Basic Science Interest Scale (BSIS) served as the instruments for data collection with established reliability indices of 0.81 and 0.84 obtained using Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R20) and Cronbach's alpha, respectively. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). The investigation revealed that the blended learning strategy significantly enhanced students' interest and retention in basic science compared to the conventional lecture approach. The researchers advocated, among other recommendations, that educators should implement blended learning strategies in the instruction of basic science as well as other academic subjects

to bolster students' interest and retention. Furthermore, it is suggested that curriculum planners promote the integration of blended learning strategies into the educational curriculum.

Keywords: Blended learning strategy, interest, retention, basic science

Introduction

Basic science as a school subject in Nigeria encompasses various science disciplines such as Biology, Physics, and Chemistry. It is a subject that serves as the foundation for applying scientific knowledge, concepts, skills, and attitude in solving the everyday problems of man. Also, its applications can be seen in many aspects of man's existence and in the recent technology development worldwide (Adejolu, 2020). Basic science as a school's subject develops the necessary cognitive abilities, critical skills, problem-solving skills, and competencies needed by the students. These competencies, according to Southeastern Oklahoma State University (2023), make it possible for students to develop their ideas and reasoning towards better contributions to society. Similarly, in Nigeria, the National Policy on Education and the Basic Science curriculum averred that Basic Science's objectives include developing students' curiosity, scientific literacy, creativity, science process skills and promoting environmental awareness towards national development (FRN, 2014; FRN, 2007). Therefore, the relevance of Basic Science in national advancement cannot be glossed over. Hence, Basic science is offered from lower basic one to six (Primary school) and upper basic seven to nine (Junior secondary school) to serve as a foundation for science subjects like Biology, Chemistry, and Physics offered in senior secondary schools.

Despite these critical roles of Basic Science, the academic achievements of students in this discipline have been notably unsatisfactory. Santos (2021) posited that academic success in educational institutions represents the culmination of educational endeavors, towards the realization of the learning objectives. It serves as an indicator of the extent to which knowledge and skills have been effectively imparted to students. Reports from the Examination Development Center (EDC) in Awka, Anambra State, from 2019 to 2023, reveal a variable trend

in student performance in Basic Science. The data indicate achievement percentages of 46.64%, 46.94%, 44.59%, 45.36%, and 48.57%, respectively.

A multitude of factors, including the pedagogical process, student self-motivation, and attitudes (Hasan, Ahmad & Razak, 2017); psychological aspects such as self-esteem (Nwafor, Odukwe & Achugbu, 2024); variables related to students, school environments, and innovative teaching methodologies (Sibomana, Karegeya & Sentongo, 2021) have been identified as potential contributors to the inconsistent and suboptimal academic performance of students in this subject. Moreover, studies by Odukwe and Nwafor (2022) and Adebajo (2019) revealed that secondary school teachers continued to use conventional lecture methods, which resulted in poor achievement of students in different school subjects. The use of the conventional lecture method by teachers, as opined by Odukwe and Nwafor (2022), has also caused rote learning, low critical thinking, and engagement among the students. To address this issue, Olatunde-Aiyedun and Adams (2022) advocated for the adoption of a student-centered pedagogical approach that integrates online methodologies in teaching and learning to enhance students' academic outcomes. The suboptimal performance of students in a specific academic discipline may stem from their insufficient interest in the subject matter.

Interest can be defined as the emotional response elicited by an individual's focus on a particular event. Habila and Benjamin (2020) asserted that interest encompasses the extent to which students are inclined and prepared to engage with tasks, reflecting their enthusiasm. It represents a disposition of readiness that individuals exhibit when attending to particular topics. This encompasses the emotions and values that significantly shape individuals' behaviors. Interest opined by Essien, Akpan, and Obot (2015) constitutes the allocation of attentiveness to specific individuals, activities, situations, or objects. Interest is essential in the educational process, as the engagement of learners is a fundamental prerequisite for the absorption of the requisite knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes outlined in the curriculum. It facilitates sustained focus, purposefulness, commitment, and collaboration with educators throughout the learning experience. Research on interest in scientific disciplines primarily focuses on

identifying various methodologies that may be employed to foster and sustain student interest in the science curriculum, thereby enhancing academic performance. For instance, Irwan, Angraini, and Tiara (2020) conducted a study entitled "analysis of student interest on blended learning in Indonesia." The evidence showed that based on students' perception, they preferred the use of the lecture method to BLS as the latter showed no significant difference in students' achievement compared to the former. Ezeudu et al. (2019) stated that teachers need to use student-centered strategies to improve and sustain students' interest and achievement. Given that students' interest in a subject increases their engagement and attitude towards the subject, their retention is invariably higher.

Retention refers to the capacity of learners to remember and retrieve previously acquired knowledge. According to Mosimege and Egara (2022), retention pertains to students' ability to recall and relate ideas previously learned over time. In a similar vein, Eze, Obidile, and Okotubu (2020) posited that retention is fundamentally the capacity to recall acquired information, especially when employing suitable pedagogical methods. This suggests that the teaching methods a teacher uses are essential components for retention. This is in line with Adonu et al (2021) and Osakwe et al (2023), who, in diverse investigations, revealed that poor achievement and students' failure to retain can be attributed to the teaching strategies used by the teachers, including lecture method, discussion, expository, and demonstration, among others. Consequently, it is imperative to identify an instructional strategy that not only enhances students' learning outcomes and interest but also fosters their retention of knowledge. One such strategy, specifically the blended learning strategy, constitutes the focal point of this research.

As an instructional methodology, blended learning optimizes students' learning capabilities and the effective utilization of educational materials by amalgamating the most advantageous features of both online and classroom-based pedagogies. As Graham (2019) articulated, a blended learning instructional strategy encompasses the incorporation of synchronous and asynchronous learning activities. Synchronous learning activities provide flexibility and ensure personalized learning. It includes online learning and recorded lectures.

Whereas, asynchronous learning activities ensure learning through physical classes, immediate feedback, and face-to-face engagement. These provide opportunities for dynamic cognitive engagement through online tools (Hrastinski, 2019). Naz, Abbas, and Amjad (2024) asserted that the blended learning strategy is vital in sustaining students' curiosity, motivation, as well as engagement. Students can advance autonomously since a blended learning environment improves range and adaptability (Means et al., 2017). Additionally, it encourages students to actively engage and utilize interactive internet technologies (Hrastinski, 2019).

The significance of BLS and the use of technology have been increasing in recent times as it is now part of our everyday life. The recent COVID-19 pandemic has also underscored the need for the integration of technology and a call for a paradigm shift in the educational sector in Nigeria. The traditional classroom experienced considerable interruption at this time, with academic institutions globally compelled to suspend face-to-face instruction. This situation highlighted the urgent requirement for learning frameworks to accommodate such unpredictable situations and ensure seamless learning (Mustafa, 2023). BLS, which ensures the joining of digital and face-to-face instructions, became apparent in the situation (Mali & Lim, 2021). Online instruction ensures that learning is continuous when face-to-face classes become impossible through students' access to digital tools and virtual classrooms. Hence, it calls for re-evaluating the current educational system by integrating online technology (Olatunde-Aiyedun & Adams, 2022). As such, BLS effectively harnesses digital and physical classroom contexts, ensuring a more responsive adaptation to the continuously evolving needs of students. The potential inherent in blended learning environments engages students with topics captivantly. The advantages of Blended learning are well explained by Selvakumar, Sivakumar, and Daphine (2020), including its flexibility in different educational courses, ability to enhance learning outcomes, learners' engagement, and active participation. It also ensures a balance between online learning and traditional lecture method, ensuring that both digital tools and traditional learning are optimally utilized. Nevertheless, Al-Samarraie and Saeed (2018) and Rasheed et al. (2020) affirmed that it is imperative to acknowledge that, despite the numerous advantages

associated with blended learning, it also introduces specific challenges, including disparities in technology accessibility, insufficient digital competencies, and difficulties in sustaining motivation in students within a digital context. In the context of Nigeria, public educational institutions are similarly affected by challenges such as inadequate digital literacy among students and educators, frequent power outages, unreliable internet connections, and a lack of access to laptops, tablets, and computers (Nwafor, Ibe & Muoneke, 2022; Afolabi and Afolabi, 2016). Consequently, meticulous planning and execution are essential for optimizing the advantages of blended learning while alleviating potential shortcomings.

Oweis (2018) examined the effect of adopting a BLS on performance and motivation in the English language using a sample of college English language learners. The experimental group comprised 16 students, while the control group included 18 students who received training using a conventional technique. An English proficiency test and a scale intended to gauge students' zeal for language learning were the methods used to obtain the data. The study's conclusions showed that students in the experimental group fared better than those in the control group and were noticeably more motivated. Regarding BLS, Hawi and Sudira (2019) employed a quasi-experimental research design and MANCOVA for data analysis and disclosed higher conceptual understanding in computer networks of students in BLS groups than those in the control group. Yu et al (2021) and Çiftçi (2020) averred that both the conventional offline learning and BLS can increase students' critical thinking but that BLS had a considerable improvement on the academic outcome of undergraduate nursing students than the conventional offline learning. Picciano (2019) and Garrison and Vaughan (2018) also affirmed that BLS is efficient in improving students' learning outcomes, engagement, and critical thinking. In spite of the broad empirical studies and the advantages of blended learning on students' achievement, there is still a gap in its effect on other variables among students, as there are limited studies on the impact of blended learning on students' interest and retention in Basic Science. Moreover, most of the reviewed studies were done using university students and their existing lack of literature on how effective BLS can be in Nigeria, whose public institutions have been

characterized by a lack of information and communication technology tools. Hence, the gap that necessitated the present study.

Objectives of the Study

1. Mean interest rating scores of students in basic science when taught blended learning strategy and conventional lecture method.
2. Mean retention scores of students in basic science when taught using blended learning strategy.

Questions of the Study

1. What are the mean interest rating scores of students taught basic science using blended learning strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method?
2. What are the mean retention scores of students in basic science when taught using blended learning strategy?

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest rating scores of students taught basic science using blended learning strategy and those taught with the conventional lecture method.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students in basic science when taught using blended learning strategy.

Methods

Research Design

The investigation utilized a quasi-experimental research design. Specifically, the pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group design was employed. The suitability of this design was substantiated by Nworgu (2018), who affirmed that such a design is appropriate when random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups is unfeasible and intact classes are utilized.

Participants

The research was conducted within the Aguata education zone of Anambra State. The population under study comprised 2,950 upper basic VIII students (1,300 males and 1,650 females) distributed across 50 public secondary schools in the zone. A sample size of 97 students was determined, consisting of 39 males and 58 females. The researchers implemented a random sampling technique (balloting without replacement) to select two local government areas (LGAs). In contrast, purposive sampling was employed to choose one co-educational school from each of the two selected LGAs. One of the schools was randomly designated as the experimental group, while the other was assigned as the control group.

Instruments

The Basic Science Achievement Test (BSAT), comprising 25 multiple-choice items derived from past Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) questions, and the Basic Science Interest Scale (BSIS), adapted from Knekta et al. (2020) and consisting of 30 items rated on a 4-point scale (Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points), and Strongly Disagree (1 point)), served as the instruments for data collection. The instruments, in conjunction with the lesson plan, table of specifications, purpose of the study, research questions, and hypotheses, underwent validation by three experts; two from the Department of Science Education (Integrated Science Unit) and one from the Department of Educational Foundation (Measurement & Evaluation Unit), all affiliated with Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State. Reliability coefficients of 0.81 and 0.84 were achieved for BSAT and BSIS, respectively, utilizing the Kuder-Richardson 20 (K-R20) and Cronbach's alpha methods.

Experimental Procedure

Upper basic VIII basic science teachers were enlisted as research assistants for the study. Students in the experimental group were subjected to the Blended Learning Strategy (BLS), whereas their counterparts in the control group received instruction through the Conventional Lecture Method (CLM). Prior to the initiation of the study, the researchers obtained permission from the principals of the sampled schools to conduct the research within their institutions. In the

first week, the researcher provided training to the research assistants. The pre-tests (BSIS & BSAT) were administered in the second week to the experimental and control groups, with the treatment continuing during that same week through the sixth week. The research assistant for the experimental group was trained in the fundamental aspects of BLS utilizing the lesson plan. For the BLS group, the classroom teacher organized students into groups and established WhatsApp groups for each. Each group was allowed to elect a leader. The teachers utilized a face-to-face instructional approach for each lesson while guiding students in using online resources. After each face-to-face lesson, a YouTube video links relating to the day's lesson are usually sent to WhatsApp pages. The students interact with each other and ask the necessary questions. Afterward, the participants reconvene for in-person instructional sessions. Subsequently, the group leaders synthesized their deliberations from the online class, while the instructor engaged with the students throughout the educational process, both within the classroom and in the online environment. At any juncture, students were permitted to pose inquiries. At the conclusion of each instructional segment, the teacher elaborated on the subject matter of the forthcoming lesson, utilizing the same pedagogical strategy, serving as a facilitator throughout the entire educational experience. Upon the completion of instruction in the sixth week, a review session was conducted for the two groups, after which the post-tests (BSIS & BSAT) were administered to both the control and experimental groups as a follow-up assessment. The BSAT was reorganized and administered as a retention evaluation three weeks after the post-test.

Data Analysis Procedure

The analysis of the gathered data from the pre-test, post-test, and retention test employed mean and standard deviation to address the research inquiries. In contrast, the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was utilized to evaluate the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Results

The study's results are presented according to the questions and hypotheses of the study.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of the pre-test and post-test interest rating scores of students taught basic science using BLS and those taught with CLM

Strategies	Pre-test			Post-test		
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean Gain
BLS	42	73.02	9.86	99.55	6.13	26.53
CLM	55	77.93	7.82	89.49	6.05	11.56

Table 1 divulges that the pre-test of students instructed in basic science through the BLS methodology increased to 99.55 from 73.02, accompanied by a SD of 6.13 and 9.86, respectively. The calculated mean gain realized when students were educated using BLS was 26.53. In contrast, students receiving basic science instruction through the CLM approach exhibited a pre-test mean interest rating score of 77.93, with a SD of 7.82, and a post-test mean interest rating score of 89.49, with a SD of 6.05. The mean gain recorded for students instructed via CLM was 11.56. The discrepancy between the gained mean interest rating scores of the students across the groups amounted to 14.97, favoring BLS. This indicates that BLS significantly enhances students' interest in basic science compared to CLA.

Table 2: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the significant difference in the mean interest rating scores of students taught basic science using strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Dec.
Corrected Model	3034.815 ^a	2	1517.407	49.289	.000	.512	
Intercept	6624.025	1	6624.025	215.165	.000	.696	
Preinterest	626.284	1	626.284	20.343	.000	.178	
Strategies	2916.923	1	2916.923	94.749	.000	.502	Sig
Error	2893.866	94	30.786				
Total	860203.000	97					
Corrected Total	5928.680	96					

Table 2 illustrates that $F(1, 94) = 94.749, P = 0.000 < 0.05$ alpha level, thereby resulting in the rejection of hypothesis 1. The conclusion drawn is that there exists a statistically significant difference between the mean interest rating scores of students taught basic science

utilizing BLS and those instructed via CLM, favoring the BLS cohort. The effect size reveals that .502 (50.2%) of the variation in interest scores of students can be linked to the treatment.

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation of the pre-test and post-test retention scores of students taught basic science using BLS and those taught with CLM

Strategies	Post-test			Retention		
	N	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Loss in Mean
BLS	42	75.24	5.52	71.07	5.62	4.17
CLM	55	59.13	4.42	48.47	4.45	10.66

Table 3 illustrates that students who received instruction in basic science through the Blended Learning Strategy (BLS) achieved a mean retention score of 71.07, accompanied by a loss in mean score of 4.17. In contrast, participants in the CLM group, retention decreases to 48.47, with a loss in mean score of 10.66. The standard deviation associated with the retention scores of students instructed via BLS was 5.62, whereas those receiving instruction through CLM had a standard deviation of 4.45. The differential loss in mean scores between the retention assessments of the two groups amounted to 6.49, favoring the BLS group. This finding indicates that BLS has a greater efficacy for better retention in basic science students than CLM.

Table 4: Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) of the significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught basic science using strategies

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	Dec.
Corrected Model	14402.698 ^a	2	7201.349	5465.308	.000	.991	
Intercept	21.517	1	21.517	16.330	.000	.148	
Posttest	2240.636	1	2240.636	1700.482	.000	.948	
Strategies	290.336	1	290.336	220.344	.000	.701	Sig.
Error	123.859	94	1.318				
Total	343741.000	97					
Corrected Total	14526.557	96					

Table 4 indicates a statistical result of $F(1, 94) = 220.344$, $P = 0.000$, which is less than the 0.05 alpha threshold, thereby necessitating the rejection of hypothesis 2. The conclusion

derived from this analysis is that a statistically significant difference exists between the mean retention scores of students instructed in basic science via BLS and those taught through CLM, favoring the BLS group. Furthermore, the effect size reveals that .701 (70.1%) of the retention variation can be credited to the treatment, which is substantial enough to be deemed effective.

Discussion

The interest of student taught Basic science using BLS was significantly more than those in CLM group. Furthermore, the effect size determined by Partial Eta Squared showed that the educational treatment was responsible for 50.2% of the variation in students' interest scores. This phenomenon may be attributed to the engaging and personalized experiences that BLS provides learners through appropriate interactions within the educational process, thereby fostering critical thinking and active learning, enhancing and sustaining student interest. The implications of this finding suggest that the integration of BLS could assist educators in basic science to augment students' interest in the subject, thereby encouraging curriculum developers and educational policymakers to incorporate this strategy into the basic science curriculum. The findings of this investigation corroborate Vygotsky's (1978) theory of cognitive development, which advocates for collaborative and cooperative learning among children and educators or peers via social interaction, thereby facilitating students' cognitive development and consequently their interest and retention. Educators play a pivotal role in guiding, supporting, and motivating children, while simultaneously assisting them in the development of problem-solving strategies that are transferable to various contexts, similar to the application of BLS. This aligns with the findings of Jiyang, Chen, Lu, and Wang (2021), who ascertained that blended exercise significantly contributed to the enhancement of students' listening skills, cultivated favorable attitudes toward the acquisition of the English language, and amplified their interest in the subject. Furthermore, this observation corroborates the assertions made by Picciano (2019) and Garrison and Vaughan (2018), who demonstrated how good BLS can augment students' comprehension, engagement, academic performance, and critical thinking capacities. In a similar vein, Naz, Abbas, and Amjad (2024) indicated that blended learning is efficacious in advancing engagement, understanding,

and academic achievement. According to Osman and Hamzah (2020), students in higher education exhibit elevated enthusiasm and interest when they partake in BLS, which aligns with the conclusions drawn in this investigation. Conversely, the findings of this study stand in opposition to those of Irwan, Angraini, and Tiara (2020), who reported that blended learning models lacked effectiveness and did not yield significant improvements in learning outcomes or student interest. It is recommended that mandatory professional ICT training be instituted for both pre-service and in-service educators by educational stakeholders, focusing on optimal strategies for BLS implementation to enhance student interest and retention.

Students who received basic science instruction via BLS had a significantly superior mean retention compared to those in CLM. Furthermore, the effect size showed that 70.1% of the variance in retention ratings can be credited to the treatment. This could be attributable to the incorporation of CLM with digital resources inherent in BLS, which promotes student engagement, facilitates feedback, and accommodates individualized learning paces, ultimately leading to enhanced retention of educational materials. The implications of this finding suggest that students are likely to retain the information imparted through BLS, thereby fostering meaningful learning experiences within the academic landscape. This is consistent with the findings of Olatunde-Aiyedun and Adams (2022), who stated that BLS significantly improves students' achievements and retention in scientific disciplines. Likewise, Suleiman, Salaudeen, and Falode (2017), along with Udoh and Udo (2020), posited that exposure to computer-based blended learning strategies within collaborative learning contexts is essential for enhancing students' retention of chemistry concepts.

Conclusion

The researchers deduced that a successful implementation of a BLS in Basic Science is significantly more efficacious in enhancing students' interest as well as retention of knowledge. The implication is that when teachers in basic science incorporate blended learning strategies in their instruction, students are likely to retain more information and experience an improved and sustained interest throughout the educational process. Consequently, this indicates that blended

learning strategies facilitate meaningful learning experiences for the students. Future investigations could explore the attitudes held by learners and instructors towards the application of BLS within secondary educational institutions in Nigeria. The limited sample size of this study may pose a challenge to the results' broader applicability; therefore, prospective studies can be replicated with a bigger sample size.

Recommendations

1. Educators are encouraged to implement BLS in the instruction of basic science along with other academic subjects to augment students' interest and knowledge retention.
2. Curriculum developers ought to promote the inclusion of BLS in the curriculum.
3. Adequate funding should be allocated by governmental bodies and other philanthropic organizations to guarantee the availability of ICT resources, such as projectors, software applications, scanners, and desktop or laptop computers, in schools.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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